

Table of Open Data

Open Data produced within the
BlueHealth project

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Name of data set	Description	Name(s) of data holder, email contact, and institution	Technical reports or guidance describing the data set in detail	Embargo period	Comments
BlueHealth International Survey	<p>Anonymised responses to an international online panel survey which was conducted between June 2017 and April 2018, from 12,663 respondents across 12 countries.</p> <p>Data are available on participant demographics, their subjective well-being, recreational visits they made to blue spaces, their perceptions of natural environments, their connectedness to nature, their responses to changes in bathing water signage, and their health.</p>	<p>Dr Lewis Elliott, l.r.elliott@exeter.ac.uk University of Exeter</p> <p>Dr Mathew White, mathew.white@univie.ac.at University of Vienna</p>	<p>Technical report available at https://zenodo.org/record/4442722</p>	31 st December 2025	-
BlueHealth Behaviour Assessment Tool data	<p>Data on a series of point observations of visitor activity to sites in Estonia, UK, Sweden and Portugal before and after interventions collected between 2017 and 2020.</p> <p>Data are available on basic demographics (assessed from observation – no direct contact with observed users), activities taking place in the surveyed blue spaces and geo/referenced location points. Data is available for use in GIS or statistically</p>	<p>Peeter Vassiljev Peeter.vassiljev@emu.ee Estonian University of life Sciences</p>	<p>Technical information on the data acquisition available at https://bluehealth.tools/2020/09/13/bbat/ and further information on application to the data holder</p>	31 st December 2025	-

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Virtual Reality survey	<p>Anonymised responses to an online survey about preferences for design interventions.</p> <p>Data has been uploaded to the website of the journal Sustainability https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410656</p>	<p>Peeter Vassiljev Peeter.vassiljev@emu.ee Estonian University of life Sciences</p>	<p>Data is available at this link: https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/24/10656/s1</p>	-	-
BlueHealth Decision Support Tool	<p>The BlueHealth Decision Support Tool (DST) has been established to guide users and planners of blue spaces in embedding health aspects in planning, construction and management of blue spaces.</p> <p>The tool is based on a review of evidence on blue space impacts on health and wellbeing, and derives action priorities to maximize health benefits of blue spaces.</p>	<p>The data are openly accessible through the DST on the project website at https://www.bluehealth2020-dst.eu/</p>	<p>Walkthrough demo available at: https://youtu.be/tYWRUo1DCdg</p>	-	-

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BlueHealth Future Outlooks	<p>A set of reports detailing interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary analyses of the local impacts of various societal and environmental trends.</p> <p>The reports feature data related to five European cities: Amsterdam, Barcelona, Plymouth, Tallinn and Thessaloniki. These data were collected using an interactive and participative approach with local experts and stakeholders. These future outlooks deliver information that could serve as useful input for local planning processes.</p>	<p>The reports are available Open Access from the BlueHealth Community on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4551718</p> <p>Wujts, Susanne, de Vries, Marit, Zijlema, Wilma, Dirven-van Breemen, Liesbet, Scoccimarro, Enrico, de Roda Husman, Ana Maria, ... Hilderink, Henk. (2021, February 19). The health potential of urban water: future outlooks on local opportunities; BlueHealth scenarios for Amsterdam, Barcelona, Plymouth, Tallinn and Thessaloniki. Zenodo. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4551718</p>	<p>Additional information on the context within which the reports were produced is available on the BlueHealth website at www.bluehealth2020.eu/research/scenarios</p>	-	-
Climate data projections over BlueHealth cities	<p>Climate projections from 4 Regional Climate models participating to the Euro-CORDEX effort at 11 km were collected for the BlueHealth Cities. Temperature, precipitation, wind and derived extreme parameters are available.</p>	<p>Enrico Scoccimarro enrico.scoccimarro@cmcc.it, CMCC Foundation</p>	<p>Data and description document can be found at ftp://downloads.cmcc.bo.it/p_bluehealth/</p>	-	<p>Please contact data holder for username and password to access the CMCC ftp server</p>